

An Explorative Study on Renoprotective and Hypolipidemic Role of Punica Granatum in Diabetic Rodent Model**Manna Somashree¹, Chowdhury (Dhar) Lopamudra², Sur Kumar Tapas³, Chowdhury Koustuv⁴**¹First Year Senior Resident at Tamralipta Government Medical College²Professor at Pharmacology department of R.G. Kar Medical College and Hospital³Scientist II, Multi-Disciplinary Research Unit (DHR-ICMR), R.G. Kar Medical College and Hospital⁴Assistant Professor at Pharmacology department of R.G. Kar Medical College and Hospital

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Diabetes is a serious threat to global health that neither regards socioeconomic status nor national boundaries. Diabetes and its complications, if not well managed, can lead to frequent hospital admissions and premature death. Globally, diabetes is one of the top 10 causes of death. However, if appropriate management of diabetes is achieved, different serious complications can be delayed or prevented. Therefore, searching of new and safe medicine for the control of diabetes and its complications is a thrust area of research.

Aim: Evaluation of efficacy of standardized extract of pomegranate fruit pulp in hypertension, blood lipid profile and renal function of diabetic animal models (induced by streptozotocin and high fat diet).

Experimental Procedure:

Type of the study: experimental observational study.

Place: Department of Pharmacology of R.G. Kar Medical College and Hospital, MRU of Biochemistry department of R.G. Kar Medical College and Hospital.

Duration: 19months (April 2021to October 2022).

The test drug was prepared with the ethanolic extraction of fruit pulp of *P. granatum* (PGE) and chemically standardized by different chromatographic techniques. Diabetic animal model (36 rats were distributed in 6 groups and each group contain 6 rats) was created by injecting streptozotocin at the dose of 60 mg/kg in adult male Wistar rats (except normal control). They were fed with High Fat Diet (except normal control and diabetic control). [1] After completion of treatment with metformin and pomegranate fruit pulp extract according to respective group (Normal Control, Diabetic Control, Diabetic with fat diet, diabetic with fat diet and treated with metformin, diabetic with fat diet and treated with chemically standardized *Punica granatum* extract @ 125mg/kg/day, diabetic with fat diet and treated with chemically standardized *Punica granatum* @ 250mg/kg/day) all animals(adult male wistar rats) was placed in metabolic cages for collection of urine samples for urea and creatinine and finally sacrificed under deep anesthesia on day 29th (after 29days of intervention). Body weight, Blood Pressure, Blood Glucose were evaluated every week. The blood was analyzed for blood glucose, lipid profile, renal function and cytokines (IL-1 beta, IL-6 and TNF-alpha) at day 28. The histopathological evaluation was done in liver, kidney, pancreas and myocardium tissues. All groups were statistically analyzed and compared within and between groups by t-test, one way ANOVA and post hoc tukey test.

Results: 1) Metformin lowered the body weight 4.52% within 14 days and 5.98% within 28 days compared to High fat diet in STZ diabetic rats. Test drug, PPE at the oral dose of 125 mg/kg significantly lowered the body weight 6.12% in 14 days and 9.81% in 28 days. Moreover, at higher dose, PPE (250 mg/kg) lowered the body weight at 7.2% in 14 days and 10.84% in 28 days compared to High fat diet in STZ diabetic rats. 2) Within 14 days the blood glucose level was reduced to 24% (p=0.009) and it was lowered to 49% (p=0.003) within 28 days compared to high fat diet induced diabetic animals by metformin. PPE at the dose of 125 mg/kg down regulate 16.6% (p=0.03) in 14 days and 41.7% in 28 days (p=0.004). While, PPE at the dose of 250 mg/kg diminished blood glucose concentration to 20.8% (p=0.015) and 44.5% (p=0.002) in respective days. 3) PPE at the dose of 125 mg/kg reduced the systolic BP to 8.3% within 14 days and 23% within 28 days. PPE at the same dose, diastolic BP was reduced to 11.9% and 11.68% in 28 days. PPE at 250 mg/kg lowered the systolic BP to 9.4% in 14 days and 26.7% in 28 days. The diastolic BP was reduced by PPE (250 mg/kg) to 17% in 14 days and 21% in 28 days. 4) Metformin reduced 31% LDL, 48% VLDL and 22.54% triglycerides compared to high fat diet induced diabetic rats. PPE at the dose of 125 mg/kg lowered LDL up to 15.5%, VLDL 62.7% and triglycerides to 27.5%. Moreover, PPE at the dose of 250 mg/kg significantly diminished blood LDL to 40.9%, VLDL to 59.5% and triglycerides to 38.4%. 5) Metformin at the dose of 500 mg/kg reduced urine volume (50.6%), blood urea (33%) and blood creatinine (53%) concentration compared to high fat diabetic rats. PPE at the dose of 125 mg/kg, low-

ered 32% urine volume, 30.5% blood urea and 46.6% blood creatinine level in rats compared to high fat diabetic rats. Moreover, PPE at the dose of 250 mg/kg, reduced 43% urine volume, 42% blood urea and 61% blood creatinine level in rats compared to high fat diabetic rats.

Conclusion & Implication: Phenolic acids, specially quercetin, catechin, rutin, ellagic acid and gallic acids present in PGE are used medicinally for health benefits, particularly in diabetes and its complications. PGE has the capacity to regulate blood sugar, blood lipids, hypertension and renal functions in high fat diet induced insulin resistance diabetic animals.

Graphical Abstract:

Keywords: Diabetes Mellitus, Phytomedicine, Hyperlipidemia, Non-Esterified Fatty Acid.

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Introduction

In India, especially in the urban areas, DM has been considered to be a major health problem. It is one of the top 10 causes of death in adults and was estimated to have caused 4 million deaths globally in 2017. In 2009 it was estimated that 285 million people had DM, increasing to 366 million in 2011, 382 million in 2013, 415 million in 2015 and 425 million in 2017. [1]

The global DM prevalence in 2019 is estimated to 9.3% (463 million people), rising to 10.2% (578 million) by 2030 and 10.9% (700 million) by 2045[2]. The complications of DM affect nearly every tissues of body and DM is a leading cause of cardiovascular morbidity and mortality, neuropathy, nephropathy, blindness and amputation. DM also increases the risk of death mainly from CVD. [3,4] The burden of diabetes can be reduced by

three choices: control diabetes; cure diabetes; and prevent complications. In modern therapy, though there are various approaches for the treatment of diabetes and its complications, phytomedicines are also preferred over the conventional therapy. Therefore, identification of new phytomedicines with known antidiabetic properties with antihypertensive and renoprotective properties are matter of research.

Punica granatum is found to contain hydrolysable tannins as major active chemical constituents and phytoconstituents, namely, corilagin, ellagic acid, kaempferol, luteolin, myricetin, quercetin, quercitrin, and quercetin-3-O-rutinoside which were previously isolated from the fruits of *Punica granatum*. [5,6] There are some scattered reports of its antidiabetic, antioxidant, antihypertensive, renopro-

protective properties.[7-11] Aqueous extract of Punica granatum fruit has been reported to suppress reactive oxygen species-mediated p53/p65/miR-145 expressions in diabetic animals. [12] But its role in diabetic complications is under research. Recently, it has been reported that catechin treatment ameliorates diabetes and its complications in streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats. [13] Therefore, phenolics and flavonoids comprise a vast array of biologically active compounds that are ubiquitous in PGE and there are every possibility to be useful in diabetes and its complications (hyperlipidaemia, diabetic kidney disease, and hypertension).

Aims: Evaluation of efficacy of standardized extract of pomegranate fruit pulp in hypertension, blood lipid profile and renal function of diabetic animal models (induced by streptozotocin and high fat diet).

Objectives: The objectives of the study are-

To develop an effective purified chemically standardized extract of pomegranate fruit pulp for diabetes.

Find out the roles of standardized extract of pomegranate fruit pulp in diabetic complications, namely, (a) hypertension, (b) blood lipid function and (c) renal function.

Materials & Methods

Materials: The following is a brief summary of the chemical reagents, enzymes, diagnostic tools, equipment, test drugs, and animals utilized in the current investigation, together with information about their diet.

Chemical reagents- All the chemicals were of analytical grade and the details are specified below

Table 1:

Streptozotocin	Acetonitrile
α -Amylase	Glacial acetic acid
α -Glucosidase	Total cholesterol kit
3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid (DNSA)	HDL-cholesterol kit
p-nitrophenyl- α -Dglucopyranoside (PNPG)	Triglyceride kit
Starch	Urea kit
Sodium citrate	Creatinine kit
Ethanol	IL-1 β ELISA kit
Methanol	IL-6 ELISA kit
n-Hexane	TNF- α ELISA kit

Table 2: Instruments used-

GC-MS (Agilent, USA)	-80°C Refrigerator (Eppendorf, Japan)
RP-HPLC (Agilent, Germany)	-20°C Refrigerator (Celfrost, India)
Spectrophotometer (Lab India, India)	Refrigerated Centrifuge (Eppendorf, Japan)
ELISA Plate Reader (BIOBASE, China)	Bio-safety cabinet 2 (BioVanguard4, Netherland)
BP recorder (IITC Life Science, USA)	Magnetic plate stirrer (Tarsons, India)
Anesthesia for rodents (Harvard, USA)	Hot air oven (Inco, India)
Metabolic cage (Inco, India)	Incubator (Inco, India)
Ultrapure water system (Wasserlab, India)	Water bath (Inco, India)
Metler balance (Wensar, India)	Electric grinder (Philips, India)
Electric weighing machine (Wensar, India)	Glucometer (Accucheck, India)

Animals used and Maintenance of animals

In this pharmacological investigation, albino male Wistar strain rats weighing 150–200 g were used. According to the recommendations of the Committee for the Control and Supervision of Experiments on Animals (CCSEA), the animals were kept at a temperature of 24°–10°C, with a relative humidity of 45–55% and a 12–12 hour cycle of darkness and light. [25]

Animals were housed in polypropylene cages that received frequent cleanings and husk bedding. For normal rats, filtered water, balanced food pellets; and a high-fat meal for other diabetic rats were made available at all times. The study's high fat diet composition is listed below. After receiving

approval from the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee at R.G. Kar Medical College in Kolkata, the animal studies were conducted there.

High Fat Diet

The following dry food components were weighed, added to a sterile container, and thoroughly mixed. To make it paste, a known volume of filtered drinking water was then gradually added. Oils were then carefully added after that. To flavor the food, 2-3 tea spoons of liquid chocolate (per 100 g) were added. Placed it on a broad plate or tray and let it air dry for 2-3 hours. After that, a knife was used to mould the paste into a little cake-like cookie (about 5 g). The pieces were then all baked in a micro oven and stored in a tight container. [26-27] every

week, food was prepared. Each rat consumed about 15 g of food each day.

Table 3:

Composition of High Fat Diet (HFD) for Diabetic Rats Ingredients	gm	Kcal
Wheat Flour	100	362
Gram Flour	100	383
Sugar	100	400
Milk Powder	100	500
Soyabean Oil	25	225
Coconut Oil	100	900
Cholesterol powder	10	0
Mineral and vitamin mix	5	0
Total (Dry weight)	540	2770
Moisture content (>60% in food)	324 ml water	
Net weight	864	

Energy = 5.2 Kcal/gm; 1 gm of Protein or Carbohydrate = 4 calories; 1 gm of Fat = 9 calories

Study Sites- The primary research site was Department of Pharmacology, RGKMC, and Kolkata. The test drug was prepared and partially analyzed in the Multidisciplinary Research Unit (ICMR sponsored), RGKMC, Kolkata. All animal trial was conducted in the Animal House, RGKMC, Kolkata (CPCSEA Regn. No.: R/N 959/c/06/CPSEA). The measurement of research out was performed in DST-FIST sponsored laboratory, Department of Pharmacology, RGKMC, Kolkata. All ground work of this research including thesis and documentation was done in the Department of Pharmacology, RGKMC, and Kolkata.

Methods:

Test drug preparation:

The *Punica granatum* fresh fruits purchased from a nearby market. Cleaned the fruits completely, cut them into the appropriate pieces, and used an electric juicer to extract the juice. The pulp from the waste was collected and used to prepare study drug. The pulp was blotted into filter paper after being cleaned with deionized water and dried in an air oven at 40°C. Until extraction, the dried pulp was kept in a sterile container. For the purpose of hydro-ethanolic extraction, the dried powdered pulp was employed.

The dried test material was immersed in 50% hydro-ethanol (v/v) and placed in a magnetic plate with stirrer at 500 rotations per minute for six hours at 60°C. The extract was then filtered and placed in a sterile container. The procedure was repeated twice. Under reduced pressure, the extract's solvent was taken out and the dried material stored in a sterile container. PPE, or *Punica* pulp dried extract, was stored in a desiccator at 4°C for later use. [14]

Test drug standardization:

By using spectroscopic and chromatographic techniques such as UV-Vis scanning, HPLC, and GCMS, the dried extract (PPE) was standardized -

1. Ultraviolet-visible (UV-VIS) spectral analysis

PPE was evaluated for spectral analysis under ultraviolet and visible light. A stock solution containing 1 mg/ml was produced in an 80:20 mixture of ethanol and water, centrifuged for 10 minutes at 3000 rpm, and then filtered through Whatmann No. 1 filter paper. The extract was then scanned using a UV-VIS Spectrophotometer in the wavelength range of 280-600 nm and the characteristic peaks were found at a concentration of 10-100 g/ml. [15]

2. High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) analysis

Hydro-methanol (methanol: water = 80: 20) was used to dissolve the hydro-alcoholic extract of *Punica* pulp (PPE) for 24 h before filtering it using Whatmann No. 1 filter paper. For HPLC analysis of PPE, the filtrate was diluted to a concentration of 1 mg/ml. The Dionex Ultimate 3000 liquid chromatograph (Germany), equipped with a quaternary pump (LPG 3400 SD), a diode array detector (DAD 3000), and a 5 cm flow cell, was used to conduct this work. The system includes a manual sample injection valve, a 20-loop setup, and a Chromeleon 6.8 system manager serving as the data processor.

A reversed phase Acclaim™ 120 C18 column (5 m particle size, diameter: 4.6 x 250 mm) was used to separate the samples. The column was thermostatically set at 28°C, the injection volume was maintained at 20 l, the mobile phase comprised 1% aqueous acetic acid solution (Solvent A) and acetonitrile (Solvent B), and the flow rate was regulated to 0.7 ml/min. By changing the ratio of solvent B to solvent A, a gradient elution was carried out. The first scenario had a solvent B: solvent A ratio of 10:90. After that, the gradient elution was adjusted to use various solvent A: B ratios, such as 40:60 in a linear way for 28 minutes, 60:40 for 39 minutes, and 90:10 for 50 minutes. After running

for 55 minutes, the mobile phase composition was allowed to return to its initial state before another sample was injected. In accordance with the absorption maxima of the examined chemicals, the HPLC chromatogram was detected using a photo diode array UV detector at 280 nm. Using methanol and mobile phase in a 1:1 v/v ratio, the individual standard solution was produced individually at a concentration of 1 mg/ml. Each substance was

identified using both its retention time and spiking with standards done under identical circumstances. The integrated peak area was used to quantify the sample, and the content was determined using the calibration curve by plotting peak area against the concentration of the appropriate standard. [16-17] the method was validated according to the USP and ICH guidelines. [18]

HPLC chromatogram of *Punica granatum* fruit pulp extract (PPE)

Figure 1:

3. GC-MS High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) analysis

By using GC-MS, the biologically active components in hydro-alcoholic extract of Punica pulp (PPE) were identified (Agilent 7890B GC with 5977A MSD, Agilent, USA). A capillary column (HP 5ms, 5% diphenyl-95% dimethyl polysiloxane) with a 30 m length, 0.25 mm ID, and 0.25 m film thickness is used to effectively separate the samples. The optimal oven temperature was programmed to start at 80°C for 2 minutes, then rise to 220°C at a rate of 4°C/min, and lastly to 280°C at 5°C while maintaining the ultimate temperature for

5 minutes. The flow rate of the carrier gas, helium, was kept constant at 1 ml/min. The temperature of the MS transfer line was set at 280°C while the injector was set at 220°C.

The organic component of PPE was eluted in n-hexane and ethyl acetate solvent at a ratio of 70:30 (v/v), dried and re-suspended with 1 ml n-hexane before analysis. [19] By matching the mass spectra to those found in the NIST 14.1 collection, all components were identified. The instrument software MassHunter expressed the SA's GC-MS profile as a relative percentage of the total peak area (TIC).

Acquired : 28 Jan 2022 17:05 using AcqMethod alokems.M
Instrument : GCMS
Sample Name : Sample 4
Misc Info :
Vial Number : 1

Figure 2:

Pharmacological activities:**1. In-vitro anti-diabetic action -**

The anti-diabetic studies with hydro-alcoholic extract of Punica pulp (PPE) were done with α -amylase and α -glucosidase inhibitory assay methods -

a) In-vitro α -amylase inhibitory action

For this study 100 μ l of PPE in different concentrations (1 μ g/ml-1000 μ g/ml dissolved in 80% methanol water) and 100 μ l of α -amylase solution (0.5 unit/ml in 20 mM phosphate buffer) were added and incubated at 25°C for 10 min. After pre-incubation, 0.5 ml of 1% (v/v) starch solution in buffer was added to each tube and incubated at 37°C for 15 min. The reaction was terminated with 1 ml 96 mM DNSA (3, 5-dinitrosalicylic acid) reagent, placed in boiling water bath for 5 min, cooled to room temperature.

To eliminate the absorbance produced by the colour factor of test compounds, appropriate product controls without the enzyme were also measured. The enzyme without sample was used as a blank. All the measurements were repeated for at least three times. The absorbance was read at 540 nm after dilution with 2 ml deionized water. [20-21] The percent inhibition was calculated and expressed as IC₅₀.

$$\text{Inhibition (\%)} = \left[\frac{\{\text{absorbance of blank} - (\text{absorbance of sample} - \text{absorbance of product control})\}}{\text{absorbance of blank}} \right] \times 100.$$
b) In-vitro α -glucosidase inhibitory assay

Para-nitrophenyl-D-glucopyranoside (PNPG) was used as a substrate and α -glucosidase as an enzyme source. In brief, 0.05 ml of 10 mM PNPG was added to various concentrations of PPE (1-1000 μ g/ml) in 0.5 ml of 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) before being incubated at 25°C for 10 min. After incubation, 0.02 ml of α -glucosidase (0.5 unit/ml) was added. Incubation continued for an additional 5 min at 25°C. Finally, 0.3 ml of 50 mM sodium hydroxide solution was added to the tubes, and the absorbance at 410 nm was measured. Finally, 0.3 ml of 50 mM sodium hydroxide was added to the mixture and the absorbance was measured at 410 nm. To eliminate the absorbance produced by the colour factor of test compounds, appropriate product controls without the enzyme were also measured. All the measurements were repeated for at least three times. The enzyme without sample was used as a blank. [20-22] the outcome was reported as a percentage of inhibition, and PPE's IC₅₀ values were established.

$$\text{Inhibition (\%)} = \left[\frac{\{\text{absorbance of blank} - (\text{absorbance of sample} - \text{absorbance of product control})\}}{\text{absorbance of blank}} \right] \times 100.$$
Table 4:

In - vitro α -amylase and α -glucosidase inhibitory action		
α -amylase inhibitory action α -glucosidase inhibitory action		
	IC ₅₀	IC ₅₀
PPE(μ g/ml)	18.09 \pm 0.004	7.25 \pm 0.02

Mean \pm Standard Deviation; N=3

Streptozotocin induced diabetic model

Streptozotocin (STZ) was dissolved in ice-cold citrate buffer (0.1M, pH 4.5) and injected intravenously at the dose of 60 mg/kg in Wistar rats (except normal control). The diabetic state (fasting blood glucose >180 mg/dl) was confirmed 3 days after STZ injection. [20,23] The diabetic rats were randomly grouped under (i) normal control, (ii)

diabetic control, (iii) diabetic with high fat diet control, (iv) diabetic with high fat diet and standard drug Metformin at the dose of 500 mg/kg, (v) diabetic with high fat diet and test drug PPE at the dose of 125mg/kg, and (vi) diabetic with high fat diet and test drug PPE at the dose of 250 mg/kg.

The experimental therapeutic regimen was as follows (n=6)

Table 5:

Group I:	Normal Control (NC) - without any treatment, maintained with normal diet
Group II:	Diabetic Control (DC): STZ induced diabetes, maintained with normal diet
Group III:	Diabetic with fat diet (HFD): STZ induced diabetes, maintained with high fat diet
Group IV:	Diabetic with fat diet (HFD): STZ induced diabetes, maintained with high fat diet (HFD) and treated with Metformin (500 mg/kg/day; p.o)
Group V:	Diabetic with fat diet (HFD): STZ induced diabetes, maintained with high fat diet (HFD) and treated with PPE (125 mg/kg/day; p.o)
Group VI:	Diabetic with fat diet (HFD): STZ induced diabetes, maintained with high fat diet (HFD) and treated with PPE (250 mg/kg/day; p.o)

Normal diet: energy 3.8 Kcal/g; HFD: energy 5.24 Kcal/g.

The freshly prepared test drug, PPE was given orally once per day for 28 consecutive days. Body weight (electronic weigh machine), blood pressure (tail cut-off method) and blood sugar (glucometer/spectrophotometer) was measured in day 0, 14 and 28.

Thereafter, all animals were placed on metabolic cage with food and water for 24 h for urine collection. On day 29th, blood was withdrawn from retro orbital plexus from all animals under anesthesia.

The animals were placed on anesthetic chamber using oxygen as gas and isoflurane as solvent in the anesthetic apparatus. Blood was withdrawn from retro-orbital plexus of the anesthetized animals. All animals were sacrificed under deep anesthesia.

The biochemical estimations of blood glucose, blood lipid profile e.g., total cholesterol, HDL-cholesterol and triglycerides, blood urea and blood creatinine were estimated spectrophotometrically (using diagnostic kits (Coral Clinical Systems, Goa, India) according to manufacturer's protocols. Blood IL-1 β , IL-6 and TNF- α were estimated using immunoassay based ELISA kits (Quantikine, R&D Systems, USA) and ELISA plate reader (BIOBASE

BK-EL10A, China) according to manufacturer's protocols. Pathological examinations of liver, kidney, pancreas and myocardium were done. Sections of the tissues of the rats were fixed in 10% formalin, processed and embedded in paraffin and stained with haematoxylin and eosin (H & E). Histopathological examinations of stained tissues were done under a light microscope for any alterations compared to the normal structure. [24]

Blood pressure estimation:

The blood pressure of each un-anesthetized animal was recorded at ambient temperature (32°C) by IITC MRBP tail cuff blood pressure recorder system (IITC Life Science, USA). The IITC MRBP recorder was calibrated the configuration before study.

Thereafter, the conscious animals were put on restraint holder and placed on instrumental chamber at 32°C. The animal's tail was passed through the tail cuff sensor. It was remain for 5 min for their acclimatization or relaxation. Thereafter, the systolic and diastolic blood pressure was recorded and analyzed by IITC Life Science Data Acquisition Software.

Figure 3:

Assessments: The following parameters were assessed –

Table 6:

Body weight:	On day 0, 14 and 28 by electronic weighing machine
Blood glucose (F):	On day 0, 14 and 28 by glucometer and spectrophotometer
Blood pressure:	On day 0, 14 and 28 by tail-cuff method
Lipid profile:	On day 29 by spectrophotometer using diagnostic kits
Renal function:	On day 28 urine volume in metabolic cage
Blood cytokines:	On day 29, IL1beta, IL-6 & TNF- α by ELISA kits
Pathology:	Liver, kidney & pancreas microscopically

Statistical analysis: All the data were expressed as the mean \pm SD (Standard Deviation). Descriptive statistics were used for chemical standardizations

of test compounds. Significant differences between different groups were evaluated by t-test and one way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by

post-hoc Tukey test. All statistical analysis were done by SPSS software (IBM, USA) and significance level was accepted at $p < 0.05$.

Results:

Body Weight- Prototype standard drug, Metformin at the oral dose of 500 mg/kg significantly controls the body weight of animals. Metformin lowered the

body weight 4.52% within 14 days and 5.98% within 28 days compared to High fat diet in STZ diabetic rats. Test drug, PPE at the oral dose of 125 mg/kg significantly lowered the body weight 6.12% in 14 days and 9.81% in 28 days. Moreover, at higher dose, PPE (250 mg/kg) lowered the body weight at 7.2% in 14 days and 10.84% in 28 days compared to High fat diet in STZ diabetic rats.

Table 7:

Groups Body weight of rats(g)						
N=6	Dose (p.o.)	Day 0	Day 14 p-Value	Day 28 p-Value		
Normal Control(NC)	5ml/kg	158.3±3.51	174.2±4.06	-	195.6±5.15	-
Diabetic Control(DC)	5ml/kg	158.0±2.64	164.3±4.04	^a p=0.172	185.4±3.22	^a p=0.163
DC+High Fat Diet(HFD)	5ml/kg	155.3±6.12	194.4±4.12	^b p=0.018	232.3±3.05	^b p=0.003
DC+HFD+Metformin	500mg/kg	157.0±2.05	185.6±3.18	^c p=0.037	218.4±2.64	^c p=0.048
DC+HFD+PPE-125	125mg/kg	153.3±4.16	182.5±3.36	^c p=0.032	209.5±1.52	^c p=0.029
DC+HFD+PPE-250	250mg/kg	155.2±1.08	180.4±2.58	^c p=0.030	207.1±2.08	^c p=0.015

Mean ±Standard Deviation; N=6; compared statistically between the groups on same day by t-test, one way ANOVA followed by post-hoc Tukey test; ^ap =NC vs DC; ^bp =DC vs DC+HFD; ^cp =DC+HFD vs drug treatment groups; p value ≤0.05 considered significant

Blood Glucose- within 14 days the blood glucose level was reduced to 24% ($p=0.009$) and it was lowered to 49% ($p=0.003$) within 28 days compared to high fat diet induced diabetic animals by metformin. PPE at the dose of 125 mg/kg down

regulate 16.6% ($p=0.03$) in 14 days and 41.7% in 28 days ($p=0.004$). While, PPE at the dose of 250 mg/kg diminished blood glucose concentration to 20.8% ($p=0.015$) and 44.5% ($p=0.002$) in respective days.

Table 8:

Groups Fasting blood glucose of rats(mg/dl)						
N=6	Dose (p.o.)	Day 0	Day 14 p-Value	Day 28 p-Value		
Normal Control(NC)	5ml/kg	76.4±5.15	82.2±2.08	-	78.6±5.50	-
Diabetic Control(DC)	5ml/kg	73.2±5.68	173.5±10.59	^a p=0.004	209.4±11.02	^a p=0.005
DC+High Fat Diet(HFD)	5ml/kg	74.0±3.61	195.4±15.02	^b p=0.043	284.5±10.06	^b p=0.019
DC+HFD+Metformin	500mg/kg	67.5±3.08	147.2±7.09	^c p=0.009	144.2±6.15	^c p=0.003
DC+HFD+PPE-125	125mg/kg	75.5±5.14	162.8±5.04	^c p=0.030	165.8±4.05	^c p=0.004
DC+HFD+PPE-250	250mg/kg	76.1±6.65	154.7±2.55	^c p=0.015	157.8±4.58	^c p=0.002

Mean ±Standard Deviation; N=6; compared statistically between the groups on same day by t-test, one way ANOVA followed by post-hoc Tukey test; ^ap =NC vs DC; ^bp =DC vs DC+HFD; ^cp =DC+HFD vs drug treatment groups; p value ≤0.05 considered significant

Blood Pressure- PPE at the dose of 125 mg/kg reduced the systolic BP to 8.3% within 14 days and 23% within 28 days. PPE at the same dose, diastolic BP was reduced to 11.9% and 11.68% in 28

days. PPE at 250 mg/kg lowered the systolic BP to 9.4% in 14 days and 26.7% in 28 days. The diastolic BP was reduced by PPE (250 mg/kg) to 17% in 14 days and 21% in 28 days.

Table 9:

Groups systolic blood pressure of rats(mm of Hg)						
N=6	Dose (p.o.)	Day 0	Day 14 p-Value	Day 28 p-Value		
Normal Control(NC)	5ml/kg	112.6±3.05	113.3±1.52	-	114.5±4.15	-
Diabetic Control(DC)	5ml/kg	113.5±1.52	145.4±3.05	^a p=0.002	163.2±4.05	^a p=0.002
DC+High Fat Diet(HFD)	5ml/kg	114.8±4.16	168.2±4.12	^b p=0.026	180.4±7.08	^b p=0.046
DC+HFD+Metformin	500mg/kg	117.0±4.05	148.7±4.23	^c p=0.038	136.7±4.16	^c p=0.002
DC+HFD+PPE-125	125mg/kg	113.2±2.64	154.2±5.16	^c p=0.002	138.5±4.04	^c p=0.023
DC+HFD+PPE-250	250mg/kg	111.8±1.15	152.4±2.51	^c p=0.003	132.2±3.05	^c p=0.012

Mean ±Standard Deviation; N=6; compared statistically between the groups on same day by t-test, one way ANOVA followed by post-hoc Tukey test; ^ap =NC vs DC; ^bp =DC vs DC+HFD; ^cp =DC+HFD vs drug treatment groups; p value ≤0.05 considered significant

Table 10:

Groups diastolic blood pressure of rats(mm of Hg)						
N=6	Dose (p.o.)	Day 0	Day 14	p-Value	Day 28	p-Value
Normal Control(NC)	5ml/kg	75.4±3.05	74.0±4.15	-	73.5±4.04	-
Diabetic Control(DC)	5ml/kg	77.2±2.64	88.2±2.08	^a p=0.025	94.3±2.18	^a p=0.008
DC+High Fat Diet(HFD)	5ml/kg	74.8±1.06	95.6±2.14	^b p=0.08	110.4±2.08	^b p=0.002
DC+HFD+Metformin	500mg/kg	76.5±3.78	85.1±3.60	^c p=0.012	93.3±3.05	^c p=0.001
DC+HFD+PPE-125	125mg/kg	74.9±1.52	84.2±3.05	^c p=0.043	97.5±2.06	^c p=0.001
DC+HFD+PPE-250	250mg/kg	72.6±2.08	79.2±2.08	^c p=0.008	86.8±2.15	^c p=0.008

Lipid Profile- Metformin reduced 48% VLDL and 22.54% triglycerides compared to high fat diet induced diabetic rats. PPE at the dose of 125 mg/kg lowered LDL up to 15.5%, VLDL 62.7% and triglycerides to 27.5%. Moreover, PPE at the dose of 250 mg/kg significantly diminished blood LDL to 40.9%, VLDL to 59.5% and triglycerides to 38.4%.

Table 11:

Groups Lipid Profile (mg/dl)						
N=6	Dose (p.o.)	Total HDL	LDL	VLDL	Triglyceride	Cholesterol
Normal Control(NC)	5ml/kg	76.66±7.02	31.05±1.08	24.33±2.51	21.34±3.51	68.05±4.08
Diabetic Control(DC)	5ml/kg	128.33±3.51 ^a p=0.005	30.08±2.04 ^a p=0.580	54.68±3.58 ^a p=0.001	43.67±1.52 ^a p=0.015	112.35±6.5 ^a p=0.006
DC+High Fat Diet(HFD)	5ml/kg	203.33±7.63 ^b p=0.006	34.33±2.08 ^b p=0.204	95.08±3.05 ^b p=0.003	74.06±2.64 ^b p=0.006	134.3±6.8 ^b p=0.002
DC+HFD+Metformin	500mg/kg	137.66±3.51 ^c p=0.001	31.06±2.09 ^c p=0.899	65.36±3.55 ^c p=0.005	38.35±4.93 ^c p=0.004	104.02±8.09 ^c p=0.045
DC+HFD+PPE-125	125mg/kg	142.66±10.06 ^c p=0.027	34.65±3.05 ^c p=0.921	80.34±5.50 ^c p=0.079	27.62±7.50 ^c p=0.011	97.35±3.51 ^c p=0.024
DC+HFD+PPE-250	250mg/kg	121.66±3.51 ^c p=0.005	35.68±2.08 ^c p=0.383	56.11±6.14 ^c p=0.006	30.01±6.55 ^c p=0.014	82.68±7.02 ^c p=0.015

Mean ±Standard Deviation; N=6; compared statistically between the groups on same day by t-test, one way ANOVA followed by post-hoc Tukey test; ^ap =NC vs DC; ^bp =DC vs DC+HFD; ^cp =DC+HFD vs drug treatment groups; p value ≤0.05 considered significant

Renal Function-PPE at the dose of 125 mg/kg, lowered 32% urine volume, 30.5% blood urea and 46.6% blood creatinine level in rats compared to high fat diabetic rats. Moreover, PPE at the dose of 125 mg/kg, reduced 43% urine volume, 42% blood urea and 61% blood creatinine level in rats compared to high fat diabetic rats.

Table 12:

Groups Renal Function Test				
N=6	Dose (p.o.)	Urine volume(ml/24h)	Blood Urea(mg/dl)	Blood Creatinine(mg/dl)
Normal Control(NC)	5ml/kg	0.60±0.20	12.65±3.05	0.63±0.15
Diabetic Control(DC)	5ml/kg	2.03±0.15 ^a p=0.016	27.02±2.64 ^a p=0.049	1.60±0.24 ^a p=0.008
DC+High Fat Diet(HFD)	5ml/kg	2.90±0.26 ^b p=0.010	33.34±4.16 ^b p=0.046	2.36±0.37 ^b p=0.024
DC+HFD+Metformin	500mg/kg	1.43±0.28 ^c p=0.032	22.30±3.51 ^c p=0.003	1.10±0.17 ^c p=0.058
DC+HFD+PPE-125	125mg/kg	1.96±0.16 ^c p=0.047	23.15±1.09 ^c p=0.073	1.26±0.15 ^c p=0.034
DC+HFD+PPE-250	250mg/kg	1.64±0.25 ^c p=0.034	19.06±1.15 ^c p=0.037	0.91±0.12 ^c p=0.032

Mean ±Standard Deviation; N=6; compared statistically between the groups on same day by t-test, one way ANOVA followed by post-hoc Tukey test; ^ap =NC vs DC; ^bp =DC vs DC+HFD; ^cp =DC+HFD vs drug treatment groups; p value ≤0.05 considered significant

Blood Cytokine- Metformin and PPE dose dependently and significantly negated all three (IL1 β ,IL6,TNF α) inflammatory blood cytokines.

Table 13:

Groups Blood Cytokines				
N=6 Dose (p.o.) IL- 1 β IL-6 TNF- α				
Normal Control(NC)	5ml/kg	54.6 \pm 8.33	128.5 \pm 6.51	14.7 \pm 3.06
Diabetic Control(DC)	5ml/kg	139.3 \pm 13.3 ^a p=0.011	210.4 \pm 16.4 ^a p=0.017	64.1 \pm 7.2 ^a p=0.002
DC+High Fat Diet(HFD)	5ml/kg	228.4 \pm 35.68 ^b p=0.047	256.3 \pm 6.67 ^b p=0.020	91.5 \pm 6.04 ^b p=0.003
DC+HFD+Metformin	500mg/kg	105.1 \pm 7.02 ^c p=0.036	160.7 \pm 6.65 ^c p=0.003	31.5 \pm 4.05 ^c p =0.001
DC+HFD+PPE-125	125mg/kg	133.2 \pm 10.15 ^c p=0.046	196.1 \pm 6.42 ^c p=0.001	46.5 \pm 3.79 ^c p =0.008
DC+HFD+PPE-250	250mg/kg	110.5 \pm 6.62 ^c p=0.021	163.5 \pm 9.61 ^c p=0.003	35.1 \pm 5.57 ^c p =0.001

Mean \pm Standard Deviation; N=6; compared statistically between the groups on same day by t-test, one way ANOVA followed by post-hoc Tukey test; ^ap =NC vs DC; ^bp =DC vs DC+HFD; ^cp =DC+HFD vs drug treatment groups; p value \leq 0.05 considered significant

Histopathology- Scattered fatty cells in small numbers were seen in the liver sections of Metformin and PPE treated animals compared to high fat diet induced diabetic animals. No necrosis was noted in high dose of PPE treated liver sections.

No lesions in glomerulus and tubules were noted in Metformin and PPE treated animals. Tight basement membrane was seen in high dose of PPE treated renal sections. Sections of the pancreas treated with metformin and PPE revealed sufficient numbers of beta cells and acinar cells. In pancreatic slices from rats treated with large doses of PPE, regenerative beta cells were also seen.

Distinct myofilaments with normal endothelial blood vessels were observed in Metformin and PPE treated animals.

Figure 4: Histopathology of kidney in different group.

Discussion and Conclusion:

There are ample of evidences that quercetin play a therapeutic potentialities in diabetes, obesity, hypertension, cardiovascular dysfunctions and other metabolic disorders. Kwon et al., (2007) showed a robust inhibition of quercetin in glucose and fructose transport by GLUT2 in Caco-2E intestinal cells. However, the two other major intestinal sugar transporters, GLUT5 and SGLT1, were unaffected

by this flavonoid. Youl et al., (2010), using the insulin-secreting cell line INS-1 β , determined the effects of quercetin on glucose- or glibenclamide-induced insulin secretion, as well as on β -cell dysfunctions induced by hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂).

They observed that quercetin potentiated both glucose and glibenclamide-induced insulin secretion. Another study demonstrated that rutin and quercetin enhance glucose uptake in L6 myotubes under

oxidative stress. Increased glucose uptake in L6 myotubes was attributed to GLUT 4 translocation, the most downstream factor in the insulin signaling cascade, which increased two to threefold on chronic pretreatment of quercetin and rutin.

In our research GC-MS study identified 34 small molecular esterified volatile components in PPE, including 5-hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF), thymine, glyceraldehyde, DL-arabinose, 1,2,3-benzenetriol, β -D-glucopyranose, maltose, lactose and sucrose. HMF has strong antioxidant properties and it has beneficial in blocking adverse effects of hypoxia. DL-Arabinose is an inhibitor of sucrase, the enzyme that breaks down sucrose into glucose and fructose in the small intestine. 1,2,3-benzenetriol is the mother substance of polyphenolic compounds and strong antioxidant and antimicrobial agent. [28] PPE inhibited (50%) α -amylase at a concentration of 18.09 μ g/ml and α -glucosidase at a concentration of 7.25 μ g/ml. Hence, the antagonistic activity of carbohydrate-splitting enzymes was thus one of PPE's modes of action for its capacity to regulate hyperglycemia.

Overall the present study showed that 50% hydro-ethanol soluble fraction of pulp of *Punica granatum* fruits (PPE), including the endocarp, mesocarp, and seeds exhibited 17 bioactive phenolic compounds in considerable amounts by HPLC and 34 small molecular esterified volatile components by GCMS. Phenolic acids, specially quercetin, catechin, rutin, ellagic acid and gallic acids present in PPE are used medicinally for health benefits, particularly in diabetes and its complications. The study also showed that PPE inhibited α -amylase (IC₅₀ 18.09 μ g/ml) and α -glucosidase (IC₅₀ 7.25 μ g/ml) and confirmed its role to regulate hyperglycemia. PPE has the capacity to lower body weight, particularly in cases of obesity. PPE significantly down regulated the blood glucose level in diabetic high fat diet rats which clearly indicate the potentialities of PPE in insulin resistance diabetes.

The underlying mechanisms may be either inhibition in glucose and fructose transport by GLUT2 or by stimulating insulin secretory pathways. The synergistic action of pharmacologically active phenolic compounds may be responsible for these actions. PPE therapy for 8 weeks reduced cholesterol, lipoproteins, and triglycerides but had little or no effect on HDL cholesterol.

These findings unequivocally demonstrate the lipid-lowering potential of PPE in diabetic high-fat-induced rats. PPE considerably and dose-dependently reduced the blood pressure, indicating the coexistence of diabetes and hypertension. 8-Week PPE therapy significantly decreased blood urea and creatinine levels. PPE substantially and

dose-dependently reduced inflammatory blood cytokines, IL-1 β , IL-6 and TNF- α . Sufficient numbers of regenerative β -cells were noted in the pancreatic tissues after 8-week treatment. From the above observations, it may be concluded that PPE has the capacity to regulate blood sugar, blood lipids, hypertension and renal functions in high fat diet induced insulin resistance diabetic animals.

Punica granatum tree is easily cultivated in climate of India, so we can produce it in large scale. It is also cheap and has no serious adverse effects. Pomegranate is easily available, affordable and safe and it will be a useful cheap supplement/medicine for diabetes in poor country like India. It can be milestone in management of diabetes and its complications in near future and for that further clinical trials and studies are necessary.

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